

PREPARING STUDENTS TO CREATE A TEXT: STYLE AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7155899>

The creation of a text by a reader is related to his ability to think independently. And the ability to think independently is connected, first of all, with the formation of one's own judgment, confidence and ability to evaluate. The formation of the ability to think independently and critically is also important in the process of developing students' text creation skills. A reader with such characteristics is usually distinguished by perseverance, clear planning of his activities and willingness to analyze and correct mistakes, to be able to correctly assess the situation and not retreat until the goal is achieved. This requires such qualities as evaluating one's own behavior, understanding and applying intellectual methods and strategies, analyzing one's own shortcomings in cognitive activity and their causes, evaluating one's achievements and finding ways to compromise.

Tasks that help improve the assimilation of complex text issues and activate thinking require:

- highlighting the main important information contained in this information, identifying key points in the text and disclosing its content;
- transfer (conversion) material from one form to another;
- reading the text and presenting concepts briefly, meaningfully and in your own words (without memorizing the words in the text);
- expression of one object itself in several variants or its homogeneous properties in their various dependencies and relationships;
- substantiation of the general theory, explanation of the information received in your own words, giving independent examples;
- explanation of the meaning of some terms, concepts and signs;
- explanation of the content of the scheme, diagrams, tables, graphics and other visual materials;
- drawing up diagrams, graphs, diagrams and images based on the content of the source text;
- bringing educational material into one system, categorization and grouping of objects;
- formation of the topic of the text, drawing up a plan (summary and thesis) expressing its content in groups in a certain sequence;

- independent compilation of questions on the content of the text, answers to questions asked in various forms.

The role of memory in the process of thinking is great. Thanks to memory, information that will be needed in the future is stored in such a way that, if necessary, it can be easily restored. To develop memory, you need to be attentive, work more on yourself.

Understanding and memory are closely related concepts, and as memory capabilities increase, if the perceived material matters, such information is better remembered when it is distributed over a time interval and grouped by content. Therefore, the main principles of using memory are: attention, ordering of the material, giving it content and scaling.

The process of understanding the text should not be understood as a process of simple assimilation of the meanings of words. For example, the text "dad brought me a gift" is not at all the sum of the meanings of the words "dad", "to me", "gift", "brought", "came". Understanding the text is always the semantics of the general meaning hidden behind the text. In other words, it is the process of highlighting relatively important elements of the text. Or is it the transformation of the thought underlying the text into an extended system. This process is not simple. This can be explained as follows:

- a) the perceived text may stop at different stages of the path along which it goes;
- b) it may end up understanding the meaning of individual words, so that the meaning of the text becomes incomprehensible;
- c) he can stay within the limits of understanding the content of individual phrases, understanding the true meaning of the current text, well assimilating the meaning of each sentence;
- d) it can penetrate deeper and reflect the general idea of the text, and it can be expressed and conveyed in a concise form.

However, this will be enough to understand the scientific text. The true understanding of works of art in this case does not pass. Finally, the perceiver of the text (or the reader of a work of fiction) is aware of the meaning hidden in the text, the motives underlying the behavior involved in the text, and the author's attitude towards people who have a motive in the process of writing this work. To understand the information that reaches a person, the form and method of transmitting information, the content of information, the degree of its familiarization are important.

It should be borne in mind that the types of texts are also diverse. The understanding of descriptive, narrative, explanatory and artistic (psychological)

texts occurs in different ways. Because each of them has different tasks assigned to them, and each requires a different depth of analysis:

- to perceive a descriptive text, it will be enough to understand the visual meaning of phrases;
- in a narrative text, it is enough to grasp the general context;
- understanding the general context in an explanatory (scientific) text is the first step to understanding, where individual components are compared, and a general idea or a general law becomes facts in the information;
- finally, the understanding of a literary text (at first glance it does not seem so complicated) moves from the text to the context (meaning), from the external content and general thought to a deep analysis of meaning and motives.

One of the most important factors determining the psychological structure of the process of comprehending perceived information is the degree of familiarization of the recipient with the transmitted material. As you know, understanding previously familiar information does not require a fractional study of the logical and grammatical structure of the perceived text, and understanding can be carried out in the form of “guessing” based on a separate previously known text fragment. In the process of comprehending previously known information, he will be able to make assumptions about the content of the text, based on one important situation. That is why the process of understanding familiar information is limited to focusing on a specific situation and relies on this situation at the next level of understanding.

In this sense, a lot of work is not required in this place, and the process of understanding the meaning is faster. The text will not sit idly by analyzing it gradually. The process of comprehending an unfamiliar text is carried out with a completely different psychological structure. There will be no out-of-text thoughts in this place, and thus the content of the information will not be successfully deciphered.

Performing the task of understanding an unknown text, the reader has the opportunity to rely on the logical and grammatical structure of the text and goes through a difficult path from understanding individual phrases to understanding the original meaning to understanding the motives of this text. In such situations, the knowledge and experience of the teacher are relied upon to achieve an effective result.

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